

THE PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS TROUGH VITAGEN LEARNING

Davronova Fotima Pirnazarovna

**Associate professor of Samarkand State University of veterinary medicine, livestock
and biotechnologies**

fotimadavronova82@gmail.com +998974089982

ORCID ID 0009-0005-0911-6821

Dusmatova Firuza Rakhmatullayevna

Rakhmatova Vasila Majitovna

Akhmadova Mokhinur Mannob kizi

Asadova Ozoda Bakhtiyorovna

Tukhtamishova Umida Narzullo kizi

Khamidova Maftuna Sunnatillo kizi

Ziyodullayeva Sarviniso Akmalovna

Zulfiqorova Khumora Bakhtiyorovna

Students of Samarkand branch of Kimyo International University in Tashkent

Abstract: This article describes the features of the vitagenic education in the system of pedagogical knowledge. Next will be illustrated the classificational, purposal and conceptual technologies of the vitagenic education. The main point of pedagogical association, subjective personalities and some of the features of vitagenic experiences in education process. Informed about vital experiences of personalities, and the role of intelligent-psychological potential of educational aims.

Key words: vitagenic education, vitagenic information, competence, macrotechnology, social pedagogy, effectiveness, didactical projection, vital experiences.

Introduction

The effectiveness of education depends on how much the teacher manages to take into account the social and individual characteristics of the children, established interests, and exciting life experience. Within the framework of the paradigm of authoritarian pedagogy, the natural life goals and values of a child, determined by the ideas o his vitagenic experience, often initially do not coincide with those put forward by the teacher. This contradiction is potentially embedded in an authoritarian model and is constantly updated in the practice of use.

However, mass education all over the world is based on an authoritarian model of the pedagogical process, since it ensures familiarization with the content of education, the

nature of which is determined by the level of development and cultural achievement of a particular society.

Methods

The democratization of society and education provides for the organization of the pedagogical process, in which its participant should strive to achieve common goals on the basis of continuous cooperation. However, the implementation of these ideas in everyday pedagogical practice is fraught with a number of difficulties, so calls for cooperation often remain declaration, “ protocols of intent “ rather than real actions. This is due to the fact that at different age stages of students’ development the forms of pedagogical interaction are different (guardianship, mentoring, partnership, cooperation and community), the functions, rights and obligations of participant in the educational process are also different. Therefore, in real pedagogical practice, it is possible to sustain interaction on the basis of only cooperation. How to create conditions under which cooperation is transformed from noble intentions into a real-life force in the educational process is a socio-pedagogical problem that has not been fully resolved. [1, p. 56-58]

Results and Discussion

The studies of scientist and educators reveal the essence, the content of interaction built on cooperation, but they are associated either with the theoretical aspects of the problem or with guidelines that facilitate the organization of interaction between teacher and student in the framework of the educational process. However, there is one more reserve in the organization of pedagogical cooperation, which has not been studied scientifically enough. This is a reliance on the students’ life experience, which is not actualized (not claimed) purposefully, is not considered as a means of enhancing cognitive activity. This approach leaves students in the position of passive participants in the learning process. Meanwhile, the historical and logical analysis of the problem shows that the idea of appealing to the students’ life experience in the pedagogical process is not new, it has deep historical roots. (Works by J.Comenius, J.-J Russo, I.G.Pestalozzi, J.Locke, J.Dewey). The role of students’ life experience in the learning process was considered in the works of D.N. Egiphany, V. Bogin, L.I. Bozhovich, L.S. Vygotsky, A.A.Gosteva, A.V. Zelentsova, A.A Kirsanova, L. Kosyuk, L.S. Kokhanovskaya, I.D. Lushnikova, N.A.Menchinskaya, M.Polani, E.S. Rabunsky, Yu.V.Senko, I.E. Unt, I.S. Yakimanskaya and others. [2, p. 45]

In the works of A.S. Belkina, D.V.Kachalova life experience (or vitagenic experience) is considered as the basis of the student’s value attitude to those received from the surrounding reality or acquired in the learning process.

There was a contradiction between the need to use life experience to enhance the cognitive activity of students in the learning process and the lack of the development of theory and technology for organizing this process, especially when studying the natural sciences. This led to the choice of the research problem, which consists in finding ways to actualize vitagenic experience as a means of enhancing students’ cognitive activity.

An analysis of the contradictions and problems of the study allowed us to formulate the topic: "Vitagenic experience as a many of enhancing to cognitive activity of students (using the examples of the course of organic chemistry)". The object of study is the activation of cognitive activity of students in the learning process. The subject of the study in the use of vitagenic experience in the process of enhancing the cognitive activity of students (using the examples of a course in organic chemistry). [3, p. 95-97]

The purpose of the study: to identify, determine the essence and structure of the personality's vitagenic experience, to justify and experimentally verify the pedagogical possibilities of relying on the vitagenic experience in enhancing the cognitive activity of students. A.S.Belkin believes that the subjectivity of the personality and its vitagenic experience will be inseparable components of the educational process in which the teacher acts as adviser sharing his experience with the student, explaining to him the reason for his own successes and failures.

The study was based on the hypothesis what vitagenic experience can be used as a means of enhancing cognitive activity if:

1. The essence, structure, content of concept of vitagenic experience as applied to the learning process will be determined;
2. The relationship and the relationship between the concepts of life experience and vitagenic experience, having, obviously, certain distinctive characteristics, will be determined;
3. Performance indicators for the use of vitagenic experience in enhancing cognitive activity will be developed;
4. A technology will be developed to use students' vitagenic experience as a means of enhancing cognitive activity; [4, p. 86-88]

In accordance with the goal and hypothesis, the following research objectives were set:

1. Conduct a historical and logical analysis of the state of the problem in psychological and pedagogical theory and practice;
2. To determine the essence and structure of the concept of "vitagenic experience", to justify the possibility of using vitagenic experience in enhancing the cognitive activity of students.
3. To develop the technology of using vitagenic experience of students as a means of enhancing the cognitive activity of students in the study of organic chemistry.
4. Determine the use of vitagenic experience in enhancing cognitive activity. [5, p. 33-35]

The scientific novelty of the study is as follows:

1. The essence, structure of the concept of "vitagenic experience" is revealed

2. The effectiveness of using vitagenic experience as a means of enhancing the cognitive activity of students is determined.

3. A technology for the use of vitagen as a means of enhancing the cognitive activity of students in the study of organic chemistry is proposed, including:

*identification of the nature, volume and content of vitagenic experiment at the initial stage of the course study;

*analysis of the essential elements, the relationship between the elements of vitagenic experience, the pattern of these relationships;

*identification and updating of implicit components of students' vitagenic experience;

*systematization of knowledge contained in vitagenic experience;

*addition of information, correction of misconceptions;

*control of changes in the content of vitagenic experience at the final stage, analysis of changes based on the developed quantitative criteria.

4. The following are highlighted as the main directions for using students' vitagenic experience in enhancing their cognitive activity:

a) activation of cognitive interest at the initial stage of training;

b) the assimilation of theoretical concepts of the studied course;

c) the formation of a holistic natural-science picture of the world;

d) transition to the self-didactic level of self-education. [6, p. 58]

The theoretical significance of the study lies in the identification, determination and justification of the essence and structure of the concept of vitagenic experience, the development of criteria for the analysis of cognitive activity of students based on changes in the vitagenic experience of students, the definition of pedagogical direction for using vitagenic experience as a means of activating cognitive activity of students.

Practical significance. The developed technology of vitagenic training, adapted to the course of organic chemistry in a secondary specialized educational institution, is effective in terms of enhancing the cognitive activity of students. The result of the study are of general pedagogical importance and can be used in the practice of teaching subjects of the natural science cycle. The scientific validity and reliability of the research result was provided by the methodological validity of the initial theoretical principles, the use of methods that corresponded to the goals and objectives of the study at various stages of the experimental research work, and the representativeness of the data obtained.

The following provisions shall be defended:

1. Based on a theoretical analysis of the essence and content of vitagenic experience, it was possible to establish that vitagenic experience is a personally

significant, most frequently updated part of a person's life experience, which forms the vitally active unity of his egocentric world attitude. The vitagenic experience of a person not only reflects the attitude of the person at the present stage, but also is a means of determining and guiding the formation of a holistic natural-science picture of the world among students, a means of predicting and creating by the person himself a new "quality of life"-that is, self-development of the person in the future.

2. Vitagenic experience can be used as a means of enhancing cognitive activity, while the technology of its application should include:

*A comprehensive analysis of the initial state of students' vitagenic experience for the implementation and maintenance of persistent motivation to enhance the cognitive activity of students.

*Systematization, addition of information, correction of erroneous ideas contained in vitagenic experience.

*Control of changes in the content of vitagenic experience at the final stage.

3. The main direction of using students' vitagenic experience enhancing their cognitive needs are the following:

- a) activation of cognitive interest at the initial stage of training;
- b) assimilation of theoretical concepts of the studied of training;
- c) the formation of a holistic natural-science picture of the world;
- d) transition to an autodidactic level of self-education.

The most important role in student's life experience I unnerving for parents. They demonstrate to children the skills and knowledge formed by them in the process of life, and from childhood help to solve the tasks ahead. The process of forming a child's life experience, therefore, is a child-parent interaction in which a parent acting as an experienced adult transfers his experience to the child. Interaction is an integral part of the pedagogical interaction. It is cooperation that plays the role of support, which helps ensure joint work for the teacher and student. And the better it is organized, the more productive the learning process. However, today's realities of education often look so that teachers assume the role of knowledge transmitted, as well as students, respectively, perceive and, as far as possible, reproduce acquired knowledge. Unfortunately, to argue about really real cooperation in such conditions is practically not possible, because it involves only a subjective position on the part intellectual and psychological potential. [7, p. 83]

Life experience is the result of the analysis of life events and their assessment. This experience for each person has an individual character. "The translation of vitagenic information into life experience is realized through the following stages".

Perception of vitagenic information .

- 1) At this stage, a person determines for himself the importance of information from the perspective of his existing experience.
- 2) At this stage, a person consciously creates for himself an attitude to remembering one or another received information.

The stage described above determine such levels of assimilation of vitagenic information as:

***Operational.** Information is one of the least importance for personal self-realization in the educational process.

***Functional.** Here, installation for longer periods of information storage takes place.

***Basic.** This level is characterized by long-term memorization and the greatest importance of information for self-realization in the framework of training. At the same time, levels can freely interact with each other degree of significance. In the framework of everyday interpretation, the process of transition of vitagenic information into life experience can be represented as follows. Events are reflected in the consciousness and feelings of a person, thereby leaving a definite trace.

Conclusion

The life experiences of each student is unique, first of all, in that he may be wrong. That is why it is always necessary to consider the so-called collective life experience. Indeed, the experience of an individual student in vitagenic learning is not self-sufficient and acquires educational significance only the ratio of the life experience of the students when there are common points of contact. The totality of individual experiments, in this case, given a new vitagenic quality. In this context, life experience does not deny the role of life information. In other words, what is lived by the person himself necessarily correlated with the experience of other people. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account indirect life experience that affects the path to success and the level of individual expectation, helping to realize the sources of one's own successes and failures. Each, without exception, personality has its own unique and inimitable life experience, characterized by its individuals psychological qualities.

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